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PUBLIC HEALTH AND MANAGEMENT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN CAMEROON

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ABSTRACT.

Introduction: At first less impacted than the rest of the world, African countries, including Cameroon, are also facing the spread of COVID-19.

Objective: This study was aimed to present the different methods or ways by which the covid-19 pandemic is managed in Cameroon.

Method: Data was collected retrospectively from other articles in a given period of time. Different information were searched and collected, then analyzed.

Results: The study revealed some plant species rich in metabolites which have positive effects in the management of some covid-19 symptoms, followed by the adherence in the age of receiving the information and on the management of symptoms related to the hygienic conditions. The surveillance was also observed to be minimal related to the test which was influenced by the lack of test kits.

Conclusion: Currently, following the findings from this study, it's clearly seen how the management of covid-19 in Cameroon was elaborated and in continuation, with the incoming of the vaccines now available to the population

Keywords: Management, Covid-19, Cameroon.

INTRODUCTION.

In December 2019, the first cases of the new severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS CoV-2) were reported in Wuhan, China. At first less impacted than the rest of the world, the African continent has been facing the spread of COVID-19, but still to a much lower extent compared to European countries. Amongst the African countries, with 18,662 reported cases (the 24th of August), Cameroon is ranked ninth with the most cases. Cameroon is the third most severely affected country in the West Africa region. The first officially recognized case of COVID-19 in Cameroon was reported on the 7th of March, 2020, and was a 58-year-old French citizen who arrived in Yaoundé on the 24th of February, 2020 as confirmed and precise by the (Bonnechère et al., 2021). Since the confirmation of the first COVID-19 case in Cameroon on 6 March 2020, policymakers, scientists, public health experts, and emergency specialists have been mobilized to respond to the outbreak, seeking solutions to contain the spread of the virus. Very little attention has been paid, however, to strengthening the PHC (Primary Health Care) system to contain the spread of the virus in communities while ensuring continuum of service delivery of essential health care (Bibaa, 2021). The dynamics and evolution of the disease vary widely from one context to another, with developed nations recording the highest death toll. Among other reasons, it is speculated that under-reporting of cases, early effective lockdown measures, young age of the population, previous exposure to other coronaviruses, a strong immune system because of frequent exposure to pathogens, and geographical and/or genetic factors contributed to mitigating the health impacts of COVID-19 in Africa. The role of traditional medicine and particularly the African medicinal plants in limiting COVID-19 transmission deserves further research in the African context (Siewe Fodjo et al., 2021).

In this paper, the researcher aims to present the different methods or ways by which the covid-19 pandemic was tackled from the beginning and how it's continually being managed in Cameroon by the leaders and authorities while taking into consideration the aspect of Public Health.

CONTEXT AND PROBLEMATIC.

Not taking really into consideration the importance of the whole health system, the government of Cameroon paid most emphasis on what could be seen after the main basic important thing that were communication and decentralization (Bibaa, 2021). Why communication and decentralization? In other to manage effectively such a situation which is mostly community based, proper information given at a time and implementing the community in the management situation will be more beneficial and easily going, permitting a strengthening and good effectiveness. Awareness, understanding and preparedness are the tools in other to have this handled and be well managed at all levels. Thereafter the incoming of the first case in Cameroon, a COVID-19 task force was formed, and international borders were closed for incoming passengers by 18 March 2020. Under the leadership of the Prime Minister, several preventive measures were instituted nationally to contain the local COVID-19 outbreak. These included: closure of all schools and training institutions, forbiddance of any gathering of more than fifty persons, closure of entertainment spots by 18:00pm daily, strong discouragement of urban and inter-urban travel, consumer flow to be regulated in markets and shopping centers, postponement of sports competitions, and observance of hygiene measures such as regular hand washing with soap, avoiding close contacts with other persons, covering one's mouth when coughing/sneezing, and other measures as prescribed by the World Health Organization (WHO) (Siewe Fodjo et al., 2021).

Currently, no approved drug for COVID-19 exists and treatments provided worldwide to the affected persons are symptom based. Globally, herbal treatments have been proven effective to control contagious disease during the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) outbreak. In Cameroon, access to health care services is challenging. One out of every 1,000 patients is able to see a specialist and 3 out of 20 patients are able to buy prescribed drugs in hospitals said by Kuete and Eferth 2010 in (Siewe Fodjo et al., 2021, p. 19). In this context, the COVID-19 situation is likely to worsen as the country moves into phase 2 of this pandemic marked by a shift from virus importation to intra-community transmission. Yet Cameroon is a biologically diverse country. This country is located in Central Africa, in the heart of the Congo Basin, the world's second largest rainforest after the Amazon. This ranks Cameroon among the countries with the highest levels of biodiversity in Africa. Despite the inaccuracy of statistics, medicinal plants are important elements

of health care services. However, access to such plants has so far been largely through traditional healers and herbal markets which are part of an informal economy (Fongnzossie Fedoung et al., 2021). However, many individuals have been taking prepared traditional medications on the bases of composition of many plants species which most call “grand-mother’s portion”.

AstraZeneca and a Moderna are two typical examples of the covid-19 vaccines that were brought up since December 2020 and a large program of vaccination was initiated in Cameroon in early March 2021 still as a method or a way in managing the pandemic.

METHOD.

A retrospective qualitative descriptive method was used by the researcher with the use of articles at a given period of time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

It was observed that, 90 species of plants are used traditionally in the management of Covid-19, with 30 among them confirmed to contain antiCovid-19 metabolites.

The study revealed a mean weekly adherence scores which were initially high, but gradually decreased over time. Predictors for higher adherence included higher age, receiving COVID-19 information from health personnel, and agreeing with the necessity of lockdown measures. Meanwhile, experiencing flu-like symptoms was associated with poor adherence. Continuous observance of preventive measures should be encouraged among Cameroonians in the medium- to long-term to avoid a resurgence in COVID-19 infections.

As regards to the monitoring of test in the surveillance, the effectiveness of Cameroon was observed to be low as confirmed by the **p-value of less than 0.001**. The issue behind this was observed to be the slowdown in the provision of test kits and in some extends the complete lack of the test kits in some centers and was still the case few weeks ago.

The above shows an incontinence in the global management of Covid-19 in Cameroon.

CONCLUSION.

By combining some simple measures to improve the monitoring, based on a regular reporting of the cases as well as a more local follow-up, and by making the population more aware of the danger of the virus and the need to adopt hygienic and social distancing practices, the constant provision of testing kits and by making their availability more recurrent the effect of the pandemic in Cameroon will continue to be more limited.

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